

HILFER MA'NOSIDA KASR TARTIBLI TENGLAMALAR UCHUN KOSHI MASALASI

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Annotatsiya.

Kasr tartibli tenglamalarning texnik, fizik va biologik jarayonlarga tadbiri oshib borayotgani uchun matematiklar orasida kasr tartibli tenglamalarni o'rganishga bo'lgan qiziqish ortib bormoqda. Ushbu magistrlik dissertatsiya ishi ham kasr tartibli tenglamalarni o'rganishga bag'ishlanadi. Dissertatsiya ishida Hilfer ma'nosida kasr tartibli hosila qatnashgan tenglamalar o'rganilib, qaralayotgan tenglamaning elliptik qismi o'z-o'ziga qo'shma, musbat aniqlangan ixtiyoriy operatoridan iborat. O'rganilayotgan masalani yechish uchun o'zgaruvchilarni ajratish usulidan foydalaniladi. Kasr tartibli tenglamalar uchun to'g'ri masalalardan tashqari teskari masalalarni o'rganish ham muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi

Kalit so'zlar: Seperabel fazosi, Skalyar ko'paytma, Caputo hosilasi, Hilfer hosilasi, Reiman – Liuvell integrali, Hilbert fazosi.

To'g'ri masala.

Faraz qilaylik, H seperabel Hilbert fazosi bo'lsin. H da skalyar ko'paytmani $(\cdot, \cdot)$ orqali, normani esa $\|\cdot\|$ kabi belgilaymiz. $A: H \rightarrow H$ chegaralanmagan, o'z-o'ziga qo'shma, musbat aniqlangan ixtiyoriy operator bo'lsin. Shu bilan birga A operatorning teskarisi mavjud va kompakt operator bo'lsin. Aytaylik, H fazodagi $\{v_k\}$ to'la ortanormal sistema A operatorning $\{\lambda_k\}$ sanoqli musbat xos sonlariga mos xos funksiyalari bo'lsin. Qulaylik uchun $\{\lambda_k\}$ xos sonlar ketma – ketligi limit nuqtaga ega emas va qayta nomerlash orqali $0 < \lambda_1 \leq \lambda_2 \dots \rightarrow +\infty$ ko'rinishda yozib olamiz. $C((a, b); H)$ orqali qiymatlari H da yotuvchi $t \in (a, b)$ oraliqda uzluksiz $u(t)$ funksiyalar to'plamini belgilaylik. Faraz qilaylik, $0 < \alpha < 1$ va $0 \leq \beta \leq 1$ oraliqlarda bo'lsin.

$$I^{1-\beta} f = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\beta)!} \int_0^x f(t)(x-t)^{-\beta} dt.$$

$$D^{\alpha,\beta} f(t) = I^{\beta(n-\alpha)} \frac{d^n}{dt^n} I^{(1-\beta)(1-\alpha)} f(t).$$

Bizga quyidagi masala berilgan bo'lsin:

$$\begin{cases} D_t^{\alpha,\beta} u(t) + Au(t) = f \\ \lim_{t \rightarrow +0} I_{0+}^{1-\beta} u(t) = \varphi \end{cases}, \quad t > 0, \quad (1)$$

bu yerda $\varphi, f \in H$, $D_t^{\alpha,\beta}$ - Hilfer ma'nosida kasr tartibli hosilali, $I_{0+}^{1-\beta}$ - R-L kasr tartibli integrali. Ya'ni bu masala Hilfer ma'nosida yuqori kasr tartibli hosilali tenglama uchun Koshi masalasi hisoblanadi. Qaralayotgan tenglamaning elliptik qismi o'z-o'ziga qo'shma abstrakt operatoridan iborat.

Bu yerda $f(t) \in C((0, \infty); H)$ va $\varphi \in H$.

Ta'rif. Ushbu $D_t^{\alpha,\beta} u(t), Au(t) \in C((0, \infty); H)$ va (3.1.1) shartni qanoatlantiruvchi $u(t) \in C((0, \infty); H)$ funksiyaga (3.1.1) masalaning yechimi deyiladi.

Teorema 1. Aytaylik $0 < \alpha < 1$ va $0 \leq \beta \leq 1$, $\varphi \in H$ va $u(t) \in C((0, \infty); H)$ bo'lsin. U holda (3.1.1) masala yagona yechimga ega va u quyidagi ko'rinishda bo'ladi:

$$u(t) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\varphi_k t^{\beta-1} E_{\alpha,\beta}(-\lambda_k t^\alpha) + f_k t^\alpha E_{\alpha,\alpha-1}(-\lambda_k t^\alpha) \right) v_k.$$

bu yerda φ_k va f_k lar mos ravishda φ va f funksiyalarning Furrye ko'effitsiyentlari, hamda $E_{\alpha,\mu}(z)$ - Mittag - Liffler funksiyasi.

Isbot. Biz bu bo'limda (3.1.1) masalaning yechilishini hamda yechimi mavjud va yagonaligini ko'rsatamiz. (3.1.1) masalani yechish uchun matematik fizika masalalarini yechishda keng qo'llanilidigan usullardan biri Furrye usulidan foydalanamiz, ya'ni yechimni quyidagi ko'rinishda izlaymiz:

$$u(x, t) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} T_k(t) v_k. \quad (2)$$

(3.1.2) qatorni (3.1.1) tenglamaga olib borib quyamiz

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} D_t^{\alpha,\beta} T_k(t) v_k + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} T_k(t) A v_k = f \quad (3)$$

$Av_k = \lambda_k v_k$ ni hamda f ni Furiye koeffitsientlari bo'yicha qatorga yoyib, ya'ni

$f = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} f_k v_k$ ni (3) tenglikka qo'yadigan bo'lsak, u holda

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (D_t^{\alpha, \beta} T_k(t) + \lambda_k T_k(t)) v_k = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} f_k v_k \quad (4)$$

tenglikka ega bo'lamiz. Bundan esa quyidagi Koshi masalasiga kelamiz:

$$\begin{cases} D_t^{\alpha, \beta} T_k(t) + \lambda_k T_k(t) = f_k, \\ \lim_{t \rightarrow +0} I_{0+}^{1-\beta} T_k(t) = \varphi_k. \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Endi bu masalani yechish uchun integral operator ta'sir qildiramiz. Bu masalani yechishni biz da o'rgangan edik va uning yechimi quyidagi ko'rinishda bo'ladi:

$$T_k(t) = \varphi_k t^{\beta-1} E_{\alpha, \beta}(-\lambda_k t^\alpha) + \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} E_{\alpha, \alpha}(\lambda_k (t-\tau)^\alpha) f_k(\tau) d\tau$$

$$T_k(t) = \varphi_k t^{\beta-1} E_{\alpha, \beta}(-\lambda_k t^\alpha) + f_k \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} E_{\alpha, \alpha}(\lambda_k (t-\tau)^\alpha) d\tau$$

$$T_k(t) = \varphi_k t^{\beta-1} E_{\alpha, \beta}(-\lambda_k t^\alpha) + f_k t^\alpha E_{\alpha, \alpha-1}(-\lambda_k t^\alpha). \quad (6)$$

(6) yechimni (2) ga olib borib qo'ysak quyidagiga kelamiz:

$$u(t) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\varphi_k t^{\beta-1} E_{\alpha, \beta}(-\lambda_k t^\alpha) + f_k t^\alpha E_{\alpha, \alpha-1}(-\lambda_k t^\alpha) \right) v_k \quad (7)$$

(7) qator biz izlagan yechim, ya'ni (1) Koshi masalasining yechimi hisoblanadi. $u(t)$ funksiya (1) masalaning formal yechimi ekanligi chiqdi. Endi ushbu yechimning haqiqiy yechim ekanligini ko'rsatish uchun (7) qatorning tekis yaqinlashuvchi ekanligini ko'rsatish kerak bo'ladi. Chunki qatorni differensiallashimiz uchun u tekis yaqinlashuvchi bo'lishi kerak. Qatorning tekis yaqinlashuvchi ekanligini ko'rsatish yo'li bilan yechimning mavjudligini isbotlagan bo'lamiz. Undan keyin esa yechimning yagonaligini ko'rsatamiz. Buning uchun (7) qatorning qisman yig'indisini olamiz va yaqinlashishga tekshiramiz. Aytaylik,

$$S_n(t) = \sum_{k=1}^n \left(\varphi_k t^{\beta-1} E_{\alpha, \beta}(-\lambda_k t^\alpha) + f_k t^\alpha E_{\alpha, \alpha-1}(-\lambda_k t^\alpha) \right) v_k \quad (8)$$

(7) qatorning qisman yig'indisini bo'lsin.

$$\|S_n(t)\|^2 = \left| \sum_{k=1}^n \left(\varphi_k t^{\beta-1} E_{\alpha,\beta}(-\lambda_k t^\alpha) + f_k t^\alpha E_{\alpha,\alpha-1}(-\lambda_k t^\alpha) \right) v_k \right|^2$$

Parseval tengligiga ko'ra, ya'ni

$$\|f\|_{L_2}^2 = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} |f_n|^2 \quad (9)$$

$$\|S_n(t)\|^2 = \sum_{k=1}^n \left| \varphi_k t^{\beta-1} E_{\alpha,\beta}(-\lambda_k t^\alpha) + f_k t^\alpha E_{\alpha,\alpha-1}(-\lambda_k t^\alpha) \right|^2$$

tenglikka ega bo'lamiz. Endi ushbu ifodani baholaylik

$$\|S_n(t)\|^2 \leq \sum_{k=1}^n \left| \varphi_k t^{\beta-1} E_{\alpha,\beta}(-\lambda_k t^\alpha) \right|^2 +$$

$$+ \sum_{k=1}^n \left| f_k t^\alpha E_{\alpha,\alpha-1}(-\lambda_k t^\alpha) \right|^2 = S_n^1 + S_n^2,$$

bu yerda

$$S_n^1 = \sum_{k=1}^n \left| \varphi_k t^{\beta-1} E_{\alpha,\beta}(-\lambda_k t^\alpha) \right|^2,$$

$$S_n^2 = \sum_{k=1}^n \left| f_k t^\alpha E_{\alpha,\alpha-1}(-\lambda_k t^\alpha) \right|^2.$$

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U holda quyidagi tengsizlikka ega bo'lamiz:

$$\|S_n(t)\|^2 \leq S_n^1 + S_n^2.$$

Endi Mittag - Leffler funksiyasining

$$0 < |E_{\alpha,\beta}(-t)| \leq \frac{C}{1+t}, \quad t > 0$$

bahosidan foydalanib, yuqoridagi tenglikning o'ng tomonini har birini baholaylik:

$$\begin{aligned} S_n^1 &= \sum_{k=1}^n \left| \varphi_k t^{\beta-1} E_{\alpha,\beta}(-\lambda_k t^\alpha) \right|^2 \leq \sum_{k=1}^n \left| \varphi_k t^{\beta-1} \frac{1}{1+\lambda_k t^\alpha} \right|^2 \leq \\ &\leq \sum_{k=1}^n |\varphi_k|^2 t^{2\beta-2} \frac{1}{\lambda_k^2 t^{2\alpha}} \leq \frac{1}{\lambda_1^2 t^{2(\alpha-\beta+1)}} \sum_{k=1}^n |\varphi_k|^2. \end{aligned}$$

va

$$S_n^2 = \sum_{k=1}^n \left| f_k t^\alpha E_{\alpha, \alpha+1}(-\lambda_k t^\alpha) \right|^2 \leq \sum_{k=1}^n \left| f_k t^\alpha \frac{1}{1 + \lambda_k t^\alpha} \right|^2 \leq \sum_{k=1}^n |f_k|^2 t^{2\alpha} \frac{1}{\lambda_k^2 t^{2\alpha}} \leq \frac{1}{\lambda_1^2} \sum_{k=1}^n |f_k|^2.$$

Oxirgi uchta tengsizlikdan ko'rinib turibdiki, agar $\varphi, f \in H$ bo'lsa, u holda (7) qator yaqinlashuvchi bo'ladi. Bundan $u(t) \in C((0, \infty); H)$ ekanligi kelib chiqadi.

Endi $Au(t)$ ni baholaylik, $S_n(t)$ yig'indi (7) qatorning qisman yig'indisi bo'lgani uchun

$$AS_n(t) = \sum_{k=1}^n \left(\varphi_k t^{\beta-1} E_{\alpha, \beta}(-\lambda_k t^\alpha) + f_k t^\alpha E_{\alpha, \alpha-1}(-\lambda_k t^\alpha) \right) \lambda_k v_k. \quad (10)$$

tenglik o'rinli bo'ladi. Parseval tengligiga ko'ra

$$\|AS_n(t)\|^2 = \left| \sum_{k=1}^n \left(\varphi_k t^{\beta-1} E_{\alpha, \beta}(-\lambda_k t^\alpha) + f_k t^\alpha E_{\alpha, \alpha-1}(-\lambda_k t^\alpha) \right) v_k \lambda_k \right|^2$$

bo'ladi. U holda biz quyidagi tenglikka ega bo'lamiz:

$$\|AS_n(t)\|^2 \leq \sum_{k=1}^n \lambda_k^2 \left| \varphi_k t^{\beta-1} E_{\alpha, \beta}(-\lambda_k t^\alpha) \right|^2 + \sum_{k=1}^n \lambda_k^2 \left| f_k t^\alpha E_{\alpha, \alpha-1}(-\lambda_k t^\alpha) \right|^2 = AS_n^1 + AS_n^2.$$

$$AS_n^1 = \sum_{k=1}^n \lambda_k^2 \left| \varphi_k t^{\beta-1} E_{\alpha, \beta}(-\lambda_k t^\alpha) \right|^2$$

$$AS_n^2 = \sum_{k=1}^n \lambda_k^2 \left| f_k t^\alpha E_{\alpha, \alpha-1}(-\lambda_k t^\alpha) \right|^2$$

Kabi belgilashlar kiritsak, u holda quyidagi tengsizlikka ega bo'lamiz:

$$\|AS_n(t)\|^2 \leq AS_n^1 + AS_n^2.$$

Endi Mittag - Leffler funksiyasining

$$0 < |E_{\alpha, \beta}(-t)| \leq \frac{C}{1+t}, \quad t > 0$$

bahosidan foydalanib, yuqoridagi tenglikning o'ng tomonini har birini baholaylik:

$$AS_n^1 = \sum_{k=1}^n \lambda_k^2 \left| \varphi_k t^{\beta-1} E_{\alpha,\beta}(-\lambda_k t^\alpha) \right|^2 \leq \sum_{k=1}^n \lambda_k^2 \left| \varphi_k t^{\beta-1} \frac{1}{1 + \lambda_k t^\alpha} \right|^2 \leq$$

$$\leq \sum_{k=1}^n \lambda_k^2 |\varphi_k|^2 t^{2\beta-2} \frac{1}{\lambda_k^2 t^{2\alpha}} = \frac{1}{t^{2(\alpha-\beta+1)}} \sum_{k=1}^n |\varphi_k|^2.$$

va

$$AS_n^2 = \sum_{k=1}^n \lambda_k^2 \left| f_k t^\alpha E_{\alpha,\alpha+1}(-\lambda_k t^\alpha) \right|^2 \leq \sum_{k=1}^n \lambda_k^2 \left| f_k t^\alpha \frac{1}{1 + \lambda_k t^\alpha} \right|^2 \leq$$

$$\leq \sum_{k=1}^n \lambda_k^2 |f_k|^2 t^{2\alpha} \frac{1}{\lambda_k^2 t^{2\alpha}} = \sum_{k=1}^n |f_k|^2.$$

Demak, agar $\varphi, f \in H$ bo'lsa, u holda $Au(t) \in C((0, \infty); H)$ bo'ladi.

Endi masalaning yechimi yagona ekanligini isbotlaymiz. Teskarisini faraz qilamiz, ya'ni masalaning yechimi ikkita $u_1(t)$ va $u_2(t)$ bo'lsin.

$u_1(t) \neq u_2(t)$ va ularning ayirmasi $u_1(t) - u_2(t) = u(t)$ bo'lsin.

U holda berilgan tenglamani quyidagi ko'rinishlarda yozib olamiz:

$$\begin{cases} D_t^{\alpha,\beta} u_1(t) + Au_1(t) = f \\ \lim_{t \rightarrow +0} I_{0+}^{1-\beta} u_1(t) = \varphi \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

va

$$\begin{cases} D_t^{\alpha,\beta} u_2(t) + Au_2(t) = f \\ \lim_{t \rightarrow +0} I_{0+}^{1-\beta} u_2(t) = \varphi \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Endi (11) tenglamadan (12) tenglamani hadma had ayirib yuboramiz.

$$\begin{cases} D_t^{\alpha,\beta} (u_1(t) - u_2(t)) + A(u_1(t) - u_2(t)) = f - f \\ \lim_{t \rightarrow +0} I_{0+}^{1-\beta} (u_1(t) - u_2(t)) = \varphi - \varphi \end{cases}$$

$u_1(t) - u_2(t) = u(t)$ ekanligidan,

$$\begin{cases} D_t^{\alpha,\beta} u(t) + Au(t) = 0 \\ \lim_{t \rightarrow +0} I_{0+}^{1-\beta} u(t) = 0 \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

masalaga kelamiz.

Teorema 2. (2) masalaning yechimi yagonaligini ko'rsatish uchun (13) masalaning yechimi yagonaligini ko'rsatish yetarli bo'ladi.

Isbot. $u_k(t) = (u(t), v_k)$ deb izlaymiz. U holda yuqoridagi tenglik va A operatorning o'z - o'ziga qo'shmaligidan quyidagi tenglamani hosil qilamiz.

$$D_t^{\alpha, \beta} u_k(t) = (D_t^{\alpha, \beta} u(t), v_k) = -(Au(t), v_k) = -(u(t), Av_k) = \\ = -(u(t), \lambda_k v_k) = -\lambda_k (u(t), v_k) = -\lambda_k u_k(t), \quad t > 0 \quad (14)$$

Agar Koshi shartidan foydalansak, unda quyidagi masalaga ega bo'lamiz.

$$D_t^{\alpha, \beta} u_k(t) + \lambda_k u_k(t) = 0, \quad t > 0; \quad u(t) = 0$$

Bundan ko'rinib turibdiki $u_k(t) \equiv 0$ ekanligi kelib chiqadi. Bundan esa $\{v_k\}$ xos funksiyalarning to'laligidan $u(t) \equiv 0$ ekanligi kelib chiqadi. Teorema to'la isbotlandi.

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